

BORROWING AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEWSPAPER LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *It is known that language develops through internal capabilities and external influences. The article analyzes the process of enriching any language, including Uzbek, due to certain socio-political conditions through borrowings from foreign languages. Our analysis shows that most of the borrowings in newspaper and journalistic texts are concepts related to the field, that is, terms.*

Keywords: newspaper-publicistic texts, socio-political terms, lexical borrowing, language development, language patterns.

Introduction

The main reason for borrowings' emergence is extralinguistic factors, such as globalization in various spheres of life, the development of high technologies, socio-cultural changes in society, and processes occurring in domestic and foreign policy. From the language development perspective, the most intensive enrichment of language vocabulary occurs during social changes.

According to linguist B.Kh. Eshonqulov, "...borrowed words are subjected to the influence of the phonetic and grammatical laws of the new language, while unborrowed words cannot be subjected to such influence." (Eshonkulov B.Kh., 1996)

According to F. Akbarkhodzhaeva, assimilation does not apply only to the field of vocabulary. When favorable conditions arise, emphasizing that any linguistic material is mastered, he gives the following opinion: "The process of mastering terms is the process of transferring elements of various forms, as well as meaning from one language to another." According to U. Waynray, "...the process of assimilation in the context of language communication occurs in the context of quantitative ratios of intercultural communication between peoples, the duration of communication, the level of language acquisition, the functional role of languages in the life of bilingual societies, the status and prestige of the languages and cultures of the peoples representing them; assessment and attitude towards bilingualism, as well as interference observing this phenomenon." (Weinraj, W., 1979)

Methods

Uzbek linguists U. Tursunov, Zh. Mukhtorov, Sh. Rakhmatullaev believes that borrowed terms can only be considered borrowed terms when they have certain linguistic features, and he justifies this by the following features:

- 1) The expression of a foreign word by graphic and phonetic means in the language being learned;
- 2) The combination of the borrowed word with the grammatical forms and categories of the borrowed language;
- 3) Semantic independence of the borrowing;
- 4) The constant use of a borrowed term in a specific terminological system (Tursunov, U. and et al., 1975).

It should be noted that in many studies, the form of borrowings in their native language and the form in the language in which the word is adopted interact with the functional value, and they classify the following features:

a word with a clear meaning can also express an abstract meaning in the new language;

when some words related to gender are borrowed into another language, they become words related to a species;

when words are borrowed, they change from a single-meaning word to a multi-meaning word;

some words can enter other languages without an equivalent;

the possibility of non-archaic words becoming archaic words;

loss of lexical independence of borrowings;

the transformation of terms from one language into borrowed words;

word-formation (Nazarov P.J., 2019).

L. Bloomfield distinguishes the following features of borrowed words:

1) The concept of culture;

2) Internal borrowings arising as a result of direct language contacts due to territorial or political proximity;

3) Dialect-specific borrowings that have entered the literary language from dialects (Bloomfield L., 2002).

Result and discussion

Russian linguist L.P. Kristin points out the need to distinguish between the concepts of “borrowed word” and “lexical borrowing” and explains this situation as follows:...” In the essence of the process used about the concept of “appropriate word,” the sema, considered different in determining lexical assimilation, is “the transition of words from one language to another” and is essential for any word, including a foreign word, such as language activity, is integrated with various

features, in particular, lexical, elements of its system, the ratio of the level of regularity of occurrence in speech, etc. (Krysin L.P., 1968).

It is known that many words were borrowed into the Uzbek language through Persian, Arabic, and Russian. There are different reasons for this phenomenon. The first is that science and technology are developing rapidly. Currently, the vocabulary of the Uzbek language is enriched by words borrowed from the English language. This is primarily related to the rapid development of computer technology.

The socio-political sphere often requires the creation of unique concepts that facilitate communication and information exchange between experts and industry specialists. The emergence of new terms and concepts is a phenomenon related to the political process in society. Print media was undoubtedly assigned the primary task of reflecting and conveying changes in language to the audience, ensuring their understanding and engagement with the socio-political sphere.

Following independence, the emergence or creation of terms alongside new concepts was observed in the Uzbek language. It is known that terms have the property of naming or creation. Borrowings in socio-political vocabulary serve as a source for enriching the Uzbek language with new vocabulary. The following types of borrowings were observed in political terms:

Complete assimilation	Complete calque	Half calque
embargo	Prezident Adminstratsiyasi	demokratlashtirish
departament	Oq uy	liberallashtirish
parlament	Liberal demokratik partiya	konstitutsiyaviy
prezident	sovuq urush	mediaviylik
ratifikatsiya	elektron hukumat	transchegaraviy

Some examples of these borrowings are in newspaper text: “*O'zbekiston Respublikasining QONUNI. Sportda dopingga qarshi kurash to'g'risidagi xalqaro konvensiyani (Parij, 2005, October 19) ratifikatsiya qilish haqida Qonunchilik palatasi tomonidan 2010-yil 21-oktabrda qabul qilingan Senat tomonidan 2010-yil 4-dekabrda ma'qullangan Sportda dopingga qarshi kurash to'g'risidagi xalqaro konvensiya ratifikatsiya qilinsin*” (“People's Word”, 2010). 28.12.2010). In this example, political terms such as “*konvensiya*” and “*ratifikatsiya*” are used as full borrowed terms. As is known, “*ratifikatsiya*” refers to the approval of an international treaty or convention by the highest state authority (entering into legal force in the same countries).

“*Saylovlarning milliy saylov qonunchiligiga muvofiq, demokratik prinsiplar asosida, ochiq va oshkora hamda yuqori tashkiliy darajada o'tkazilishida fuqarolarning huquqiy madaniyati, mamlakatimizda kechayotgan islohotlarga daxldorlik tuyg'usi, ijtimoiy-siyosiy faolligi muhim ahamiyatga egadir*” (“People's Word”, 2016). The example uses the term “*demokratik prinsiplar*”.

Refer to the newspaper text: “*Bunda iqtisodiy xizmat va tovarlar uchun hisob-kitoblar elektron pul orqali amalga oshiriladi*”; “*Raqamli iqtisodiyot raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan, elektron biznes, elektron tijorat bilan bog'langan, raqamli tovar va xizmatlar ishlab chiqarayotgan va taqdim etayotgan iqtisodiy faoliyatdir*”; “*... transchegaraviy biznes hamkorlik, elektron tijoriy maydon, masofaviy ofis kabilarni qamrab oladi*” (“New Uzbekistan”, 2020).

In the examples, new terms such as *elektron pul*, *raqamli texnologiyalar*, *elektron biznes*, *elektron tijorat*, *raqamli tovar*, *raqamli xizmatlar*, *transchegaraviy biznes*, *elektron tijoriy maydon*, *masofaviy ofis* have occurred and entered the consumption of a wide audience. It should also be noted that these terms were formed by combining economic and internet terms.

“Sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalarini jadal joriy etish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish chora-tadbirlari to’g’risida”gi, “Elektron tijorat ma’murchiligini takomillashtirish va uni yanada rivojlantirish uchun kulay sharoitlar yaratish to’g’risida”gi karorlari Uchinchi Raqamli Renessansga poydevor qo’yishda dasturulamal bo’lib xizmat kiladi” (“People's Word”, 2022).

“Глава государства предложил реализовать до 2030 года “Цифровой Узбекистан – 2030” (“People's word”, 2018); До 1 мая 2026 года в рамках проектов внедрения технологий искусственного интеллекта будут запущены вычислительные мощности, предназначенные для обработки данных (“People's word”, 2024); В Стратегии «Узбекистан-2030» поставлена цель войти в топ–30 Рейтинга электронного правительства ООН (Saidov A., 2024); Цифровая среда: эпоха перемен (uzbekistan.org.ua, 2024); Президент утвердил реализацию программы “Цифровой Ташкент” (gazeta.uz, 2020); Электронная торговля в мире и Узбекистане; Электронная коммерция по своей скорости и себестоимости стала более эффективным инструментом торговли... так как все операции можно проводить в онлайн-режиме (Irgashev B., 2020); Новый Узбекистан – это общество и государство, где высшей ценностью являются человек и интересы народа (polito.uz., 2021).

Conclusion

As noted above, Russian newspapers show that some words can enter other languages without alternatives, which is why socio-political concepts from Uzbekistan penetrate Russian. This, in turn, provides grounds for considering Russian words as a factor determining the development of the Uzbek language in the context of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the objective coverage of news, changes occurring abroad and in our country, visits, meetings of heads of state, the adoption of new laws, socio-political and cultural events and phenomena occurring on the international stage, and

information about banking and exchange activities are of significant social importance. In the context of globalization, the rapid delivery of news to the audience and the expression of new concepts are clear manifestations of assimilation.

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O'ZLASHMALAR GAZETA TILI TARAQQIYOTIDAGI MUHIM OMIL SIFATIDA

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Annotatsiya. *Ma'lumki, til ichki imkoniyatlar va tashqi ta'sirlar evaziga taraqqiy etadi. Maqolada har qanday tilning, shu jumladan, o'zbek tilining muayyan ijtimoiy-siyosiy sharoit tufayli chet tillardan o'zlashmalar hisobiga boyib borishi jarayoni tahlilga tortilgan. Tahlillarimiz gazeta-publitsistik matnlardagi o'zlashmalarning aksariyati sohaga oid tushunchalar, ya'ni terminlar ekanligini ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: gazeta-publitsistik matnlari, ijtimoiy-siyosiy terminlar, leksik o'zlashmalar, til taraqqiyoti, til qonuniyatlari.